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Neuron numbers link innovativeness with both absolute and relative brain size

Authors: Daniel Sol^{1†}, Seweryn Olkowicz², Ferran Sayol³, Martin Kocourek²,
Yicheng Zhang², Lucie Marhounová², Christin Osadnik⁴, Eva Corssmit¹, Joan
Garcia-Porta⁵, Thomas E. Martin⁶, Louis Lefebvre^{7†}, Pavel Němec^{2†}

Affiliations:

¹CSIC-CREAF (Centre for Ecological Research and Applied Forestries),
Cerdanyola del Vallès, Catalonia E-08193, Spain

²Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czech
Republic

³Centre for Biodiversity and Environment Research, Department of Genetics,
Evolution and Environment, University College London, London, UK

⁴Department of General Zoology, University of Duisburg-Essen, Essen, Germany

⁵Department of Biology, Washington University in St. Louis, MO, 63130, USA

⁶Montana Cooperative Wildlife Research Unit, University of Montana, Missoula, MT
USA

⁷Department of Biology, McGill University, Montréal, Québec, Canada

†Corresponding authors Emails: d.sol@creaf.uab.cat; louis.lefebvre@mcgill.ca;
pgnemec@natur.cuni.cz.

Short Title: Brains, neurons and cognition

32 **Abstract**

33 A longstanding issue in biology is whether the intelligence of animals can be predicted
34 by absolute or relative brain size. However, progress has been hampered by an
35 insufficient understanding of how neuron numbers shape internal brain organization
36 and cognitive performance. Based on estimations of neuron numbers for 111 bird
37 species, we show here that the number of neurons in the pallial telencephalon is
38 positively associated with a major expression of intelligence: innovation propensity.
39 The number of pallial neurons, in turn, is greater in brains that are larger in both
40 absolute and relative terms, and positively co-varies with longer post-hatching
41 development periods. Thus, our analyses show that neuron numbers link cognitive
42 performance to both absolute and relative brain size through developmental
43 adjustments. These findings help unify neuro-anatomical measures at multiple levels,
44 reconciling contradictory views over the biological significance of brain expansion.
45 The results also highlight the value of a life history perspective to advance our
46 understanding of the evolutionary bases of the connections between brain and
47 cognition.

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59 **Main**

60 Encephalization—the evolutionary increase of the brain beyond that expected for a
61 given body size¹—has long been thought to be a major factor in the evolution of
62 intelligence^{2,3}. Comparisons across species have provided some support for this
63 theory, showing that encephalization is associated with several facets of intelligence
64 like innovativeness, learning and culture⁴⁻⁸. The theory has also stimulated an
65 extended research program on the ecological and evolutionary implications of brain
66 size and architecture⁹⁻¹¹. Yet, the reasons why a disproportionately larger brain should
67 provide cognitive advantages remain unclear^{3,12,13}.

68 The rationale of the encephalization theory, as originally envisioned by
69 Jerison¹⁴, is that the “extra tissue” that makes the brain larger than expected for a given
70 body size (i.e., larger relative brain size) reflects extra neurons that are available for
71 cognitive tasks. However, the notion that cognitive performance depends on neuron
72 numbers and increases with encephalization is backed by insufficient evidence^{3,15,16}.
73 Moreover, given that neuron numbers increase with absolute brain size^{3,17}, should we
74 not expect that cognitive differences across species will be better predicted by
75 absolute rather than relative brain size? There is indeed evidence that absolute brain
76 size sometimes predicts cognitive performance across species better than relative
77 measures of the brain¹⁸⁻²⁰. Such results are not surprising given that increases in
78 relative brain size can be reached by both brain enlargement and body size reduction,
79 and therefore may not always be associated with an increase in brain information-
80 processing capacity^{21,22}. The debate regarding the biological significance of absolute
81 and relative brain sizes has been further complicated by the finding that not all brains
82 are made in the same way; rather, brains may show different neuron densities and
83 distributions among brain areas across species^{12,15,23-25}. Thus, the intuitively appealing
84 notion that larger brains translate into greater intelligence remains contentious^{3,12,13}.

85 To address this longstanding controversy, we provide theoretical and
86 empirical grounds for the hypothesis that increased intelligence—operationally
87 defined here as the ability to solve problems through mental or behavioural
88 flexibility³—requires brains that are large in both absolute and relative terms (**Fig.**
89 **1**). This possibility has probably gone unrecognized because previous studies have
90 used an 'either-or' approach and pitted absolute against relative brain size
91 measures^{18,20}. Yet if enhanced cognition requires more neurons in sensory, associative

92 and premotor areas of the telencephalon —the pallial areas in birds and the neocortex
93 in mammals^{3,24} — and these areas represent a large fraction of the telencephalon and
94 the whole brain²⁶, then the accumulation of a disproportionately large number of
95 pallial neurons should produce brains that are larger both in absolute terms and
96 relative to body size^{27,28}. Such co-variation between absolute and relative brain size
97 should be more accentuated if the selective advantages of accumulating greater
98 numbers of pallial neurons is higher for larger species than for small ones. This is to
99 be expected because body size is a major correlate of longevity²⁹, and a long life
100 increases the fitness value of gathering information and learning^{30–33} while reducing
101 the costs of delaying reproduction^{34,35}. One mechanism that may allow a greater
102 accumulation of pallial neurons is, according to some evo-devo models, an extension
103 of development periods, particularly the later stages in altricial offspring that are born
104 underdeveloped^{36,37}. Thus, selection on cognition might link intelligence with larger
105 absolute and relative brain size through developmental adjustments (**Fig. 1**).

106 Testing the above tenets is challenging owing to the difficulties of accurately
107 estimating neuron numbers of different brain regions for many species¹⁵. The isotropic
108 fractionator—a new method of assessing neuron numbers developed by Herculano-
109 Houzel and collaborators³⁸— now makes it possible. Our study is based on a
110 substantially updated dataset^{24,25,39} quantifying neuron numbers in the whole brain
111 and three brain areas (the pallium, the cerebellum and the brainstem) for 111 species
112 of 24 avian families, representing both basal and crown avian lineages (**Fig. 1e**;
113 **Supplementary Fig. 1**) and encompassing a large fraction of the morphospace
114 occupied by avian brains (**Supplementary Fig. 2**). To test associations with cognition,
115 we focus on a major component of intelligence, innovativeness⁴⁰, by quantifying its
116 product —innovation frequency^{4–6,41}. Our innovation data were extracted from a
117 database including >4400 published reports of bird species using novel foods or new
118 feeding techniques in the wild⁴². On this basis, we first ask whether innovation
119 propensity increases with the number of neurons in the pallium (and potentially also
120 in the cerebellum, which is thought to co-evolve and function in tandem with the
121 pallium^{43,44}), but not with those in areas less directly involved in cognition like the
122 brainstem. Next, we investigate whether the proliferation of neurons in the pallium
123 makes the brain increase disproportionately with body size, linking innovativeness
124 with both absolute and relative brain size. Finally, we test whether the accumulation
125 of neurons in the pallium is associated with an extension of later stages of

126 development. We test these predictions by combining random forests, a type of
127 machine-learning algorithm that allows us to accommodate complex non-linear
128 interactions among predictors with minimal assumptions⁴⁵, with Bayesian mixed
129 models that explicitly account for phylogenetic relatedness among species⁴⁶. Because
130 nocturnal species are difficult to observe, and hence are not present in the innovation
131 data set, we exclude owls from all the analyses that follow; results with the entire
132 dataset are shown in the Supplementary Information.

133

134 **Results and discussion**

135 Cognitive performance has long been thought to depend on the number of
136 neurons in the brain^{47,48}, but this hypothesis is currently backed by surprisingly little
137 empirical evidence¹⁵. A comparison of apes, corvids and pigeons in five cognitive
138 domains concluded that neuron number is a poor predictor of absolute cognitive
139 performance, but it may predict learning speed and the ability to plastically adjust
140 rules to novel situations⁴⁷. A broader comparative analysis across primates and birds
141 revealed that performance in a cognitive task (the detour test) does tend to increase
142 with the total number of cortical/pallial neurons¹⁵, yet this study did not rule out the
143 possibility that the association was driven by phylogenetic relatedness.

144 Using Bayesian phylogenetic mixed models, we found that the number of
145 neurons in the entire brain is positively associated with behavioural innovation
146 propensity (**Fig. 2a**), particularly technical innovations that are assumed to require
147 more advanced cognition⁵ (**Supplementary Table 1**). The pattern holds when body
148 mass is included as a covariate in the model (**Fig. 2b**; **Supplementary Table 2**),
149 suggesting that innovation propensity is higher in birds with a disproportionately
150 larger number of neurons than expected on the basis of body size. While we find that
151 the brain of innovative species contains more neurons than the brain of less innovative
152 species, there is no parallel increase in neuron density; rather, innovation propensity
153 decreases with neuron density (**Fig. 2c**). Because avian neuron densities tend to
154 decrease with brain size and the total number of neurons, these results support the
155 notion that cognitive performance is primarily limited by the absolute and relative
156 number of neurons rather than by neuron densities.

157 Additional analyses revealed that the number of neurons in the pallium and, to
158 a lesser extent, the cerebellum are better predictors of innovation propensity than
159 neurons in the brainstem, a brain area less directly involved in cognition (**Fig. 2**;

160 **Supplementary Tables 1 and 2**). Although pallial areas are thought to co-evolve and
161 function in tandem with the cerebellum^{43,44}, it remains to be determined whether the
162 avian cerebellum subserves motor skills only (as its association with technical
163 innovations but not resource innovations suggests; **Supplementary Tables 2**) or is
164 also directly involved in cognitive functions like the mammalian cerebellum⁴³.
165 Nonetheless, our findings align with growing evidence that cognitive processes
166 associated with intelligence are controlled by widely-distributed networks integrating
167 several brain areas⁴⁹.

168 Corvids and parrots are regarded as the most innovative birds, a conclusion
169 that is backed by ample experimental evidence^{47,48,50,51}. These taxa also share both the
170 highest inferred rates of brain-body size evolution among Neoaves and the steepest
171 allometric slopes among all birds⁵². This contrasts with less innovative taxa like early-
172 diverging birds (Palaeognathae, basal Neognathae), Anseriformes (waterfowl), and
173 predatory core landbirds (hawks & eagles, falcons and owls), whose allometric
174 exponents have diverged little from the ancestral avian grade and hence represent low-
175 slope grades. To assess whether the proliferation of neurons in the pallium can explain
176 deviations from the “ancestral” allometric scaling relationship, we estimated the
177 allometric exponents of the neuron numbers for clades with the highest slope and low-
178 slope grades (sensu⁵²); we then compared these with the allometric exponents for the
179 cerebellum and brainstem. We find that while the allometric exponents for the
180 cerebellum and brainstem were similar between the two slope grade groups, clades
181 that share a high slope tended to accumulate disproportionately more neurons in the
182 pallium as they become larger (**Fig. 3, Supplementary Figs. 3-5**). Thus, as expected,
183 the accumulation of pallial neurons makes the brain increase in both absolute and
184 relative terms (**Fig. 4, Supplementary Figs. 6 and 7**).

185 While the number of neurons in the whole brain and the pallium increases in
186 a similar way with both absolute and relative brain size (**Fig. 4**), the number of neurons
187 in the cerebellum is more strongly related to absolute brain size alone; those in the
188 brainstem do not follow any clear pattern. These conclusions are consistent regardless
189 of the method used to estimate relative brain size (**Supplementary Fig. 7**); they also
190 hold when we include owls (**Supplementary Figs. 6 and 7**), whose large forebrain
191 results in part from expanding the visual Wulst for sensory rather than associative
192 purposes. Although the evolutionary repatterning of the brain-body relationship
193 cannot be circumscribed to selection on brain size alone, our results support the notion

194 that cognition can form a major driver of adaptive shifts to higher grades deviations
195 from the “ancestral” allometric scaling.

196 Presumably because brain cellular scaling rules can be clade-specific^{15,23–25,53}
197 and because avian neuron densities decrease with brain mass^{24,25}, the relationship
198 between neuron numbers and brain size is complex. The relationship tends to be
199 roughly linear for relative brain size, especially when we exclude owls, but only for
200 the entire brain and the pallium (**Fig. 4b**). In contrast, neuron numbers tend to
201 asymptote at larger absolute brain sizes in all cases (**Fig. 4c**). This latter finding agrees
202 with the notion that animals that have large brains merely because they have very big
203 bodies are not necessarily the most intelligent, as it is the case for Ratites and large
204 Galliformes.

205 Several developmental mechanisms, including differences in early morphogen
206 patterning and expansion of stem cell pool, diversification of neural progenitors,
207 variation of cell-cycle rates and protracted neurogenesis are responsible for expansion
208 of the telencephalon in amniotes^{37,54–56}. We asked whether these mechanisms were
209 reflected in the duration of embryonic and post-hatching development periods. We
210 found that longer development time leads to a greater accumulation of number of
211 neurons in the pallium of clades with high-slope grades than in those showing low-
212 slope grades (**Fig. 5; Supplementary Fig. 8**). This accumulation of neurons is
213 associated with an extension of the post-natal (fledging) development relative to the
214 embryonic period. Importantly, scaling of pallial neuron counts with development
215 strongly resembles that found for the total number of brain neurons, reinforcing the
216 notion that the number of pallial neurons largely accounts for the much larger number
217 of neurons in the brains of altricial species.

218 Growing evidence suggests that different mechanisms underlie telencephalon
219 growth and maturation in precocial and altricial birds, leading to relatively larger
220 relative brains in the latter. Precocial birds like ducks and grouse enlarge their
221 telencephalon early in development (before the onset of neurogenesis) presumably by
222 an increase in the number of telencephalic progenitors⁵⁷. In contrast, expansion of the
223 telencephalon in altricial birds like songbirds and parrots is associated with protracted
224 neurogenesis and delayed neuronal maturation⁵⁸. Our analyses are consistent with
225 these patterns (**Supplementary Fig. 9**), showing that longer development time leads
226 to greater accumulation of neurons in the pallium in altricial than in precocial species.
227 Indeed, all species from our data set belonging to the highest slope grade category

228 show high degree of altriciality (i.e. they are classified as super-altricial). Altogether,
229 our results are consistent with the view that increases in absolute and relative brain
230 size are made possible through the evolutionary transition to altriciality and changes
231 in neurogenesis schedules related to a disproportionate lengthening of the later stages
232 of development. While this pattern is predicted by some models of brain development,
233 like the 'late is large' rule³⁷, additional research is needed to elucidate the exact
234 mechanisms.

235 Our analyses unify neuro-anatomical measures at multiple levels. First, we
236 provide firm support for the intuitively appealing notion that cognitive performance
237 is limited by the number of neurons in the pallium and, to a lesser extent, the
238 cerebellum. Thus, our results support the hypothesis¹⁴ that intelligence reflects a
239 disproportionate allocation of neurons to cognitive tasks, but also aligns with
240 suggestions that cognitive performance ultimately depends on the total number of
241 neurons and the way neurons connect different brain areas^{3,15,23}. Second, we show that
242 an increase in the number of neurons in the areas most closely involved in cognitive
243 performance, the pallium, increases brain size in both absolute and relative terms.
244 Although the number of neurons in the cerebellum scaled primarily with absolute
245 brain size, the effect of total neuron numbers on relative brain size persisted because
246 in birds larger brains contain increasing proportions of neurons in the pallium and
247 decreasing proportions in the cerebellum and other brain regions²⁴. Third, we provide
248 an adaptive explanation for some of the patterns of brain-body co-variation in deep
249 time detected by Ksepka et al.⁵²: Clades that have a higher brain-body slope than
250 others tend to be the ones that are most innovative. A higher brain-body slope means
251 that as body size gets bigger, the brain increases disproportionately more in size than
252 it does in non-innovative clades; this increase in both absolute and relative brain size
253 is, according to our analyses, mostly due to an increase in pallial neurons. Finally, we
254 provide a developmental rationale for the observed patterns, suggesting that the
255 elongation of the fledging period in altricial species links neuron numbers with
256 absolute and relative brain size. The failure to find a similar pattern in precocial
257 species supports the notion that not all brains are made in a same way^{25,53}, highlighting
258 the key role of life history in brain evolution (**Supplementary Fig. 10**).

259 The reason why the dual role of absolute and relative brain size in cognition
260 has been under-appreciated in the past probably reflects the common practice of
261 removing the allometric effects of body size in comparative analyses of brain size. As

262 suggested by Jerison², this is probably legitimate when comparing brains of species
263 with striking differences in body size, like an ostrich and a hummingbird. Yet by
264 treating body size as a statistical nuisance, we appear to be missing important
265 information. A larger body is often associated with greater longevity⁵⁹ and can reduce
266 juvenile mortality risk³⁵, which should increase the value of learning and reduce the
267 costs of a long development time^{30,31,60}. Alternatively, the same environmental
268 pressures that favour a slow pace of life could generate correlated selection on both
269 cognition and body size³¹. Whether a large body facilitates selection for cognition or
270 co-varies with cognition due to either correlated selection or shared developmental
271 processes, the consequence for functional architecture of the brain is to link neuron
272 numbers and cognitive performance to both absolute and relative brain size.

273

274 **Methods**

275 **Neuron numbers estimation.** Our study is based on an updated database quantifying neuron
276 numbers in the whole brain and three brain areas – the pallium (comprising the hyperpallium,
277 mesopallium, nidopallium, acropallium and hippocampus), the cerebellum and the brainstem
278 (comprising the medula oblongata and midbrain tegmentum) for bird species. Information for
279 65 avian species were extracted from the literature^{24,25}. Numbers of brain, pallial and
280 cerebellar neurons for an additional 81 individuals representing 46 species and number of
281 brainstem neurons for an additional 172 individuals representing 83 avian species were newly
282 estimated using the isotropic fractionator, following experimental procedures described in
283 Olkowicz *et al.*²⁴. Briefly, animals were killed by an overdose of halothane, weighed and
284 immediately perfused transcardially with warmed phosphate-buffered saline containing 0.1%
285 heparin followed by cold phosphate-buffered 4% paraformaldehyde solution. The brains were
286 immediately removed, weighted, postfixed for an additional 7-21 days and then dissected into
287 the examined brain divisions. The cerebral hemispheres (including the olfactory bulbs) were
288 detached from the diencephalon by a straight cut separating the subpallium from the thalamus.
289 The cerebellum was cut off at the surface of the brainstem. The tectum (optic lobe) was
290 bilaterally excised from the surface of the brainstem. The excised parts included most of the
291 tectal gray, optic tectum and torus semicircularis. The remaining structures were dissected
292 into diencephalon (rostral part) and brainstem (caudal part comprising the medula oblongata
293 and midbrain tegmentum) along the plane connecting the posterior commissure dorsally and
294 hypothalamus-mesencephalon boundary ventrally. The latter is visible macroscopically as a
295 groove between the convex ventral part of the midbrain and the hypothalamus, caudally to
296 the infundibulum and mammillary bodies. In one individual per species, one hemisphere was

297 dissected into the pallium and the subpallium. These hemispheres were embedded in agarose
298 and sectioned on a vibratome at 300–500 μm (depending on size of a hemisphere) in the
299 coronal plane. Under oblique transmitted light at the stereomicroscope and with the use of a
300 microsurgical knife (Stab Knife Straight, 5.5 mm, ref 7516, Surgical Specialities Corporation,
301 Reading, PA, USA) we manually dissected the pallium from subpallium on each section by
302 cutting along the pallial-subpallial lamina, as defined by Reiner et al.⁶².

303 The dissected structures were dried with a paper towel, weighed to the nearest 0.1
304 milligram, incubated in 30% sucrose solution until they sank, then transferred into antifreeze
305 (30% glycerol, 30% ethylene glycol, 40% phosphate buffer) and frozen for further processing.
306 The examined brain parts were homogenized in 40 mM sodium citrate with 1% Triton X-100
307 using Tenbroeck tissue grinders (Wheaton, Millville, NY, USA) to obtain a suspension of free
308 cell nuclei. The fluorescent DNA marker 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) was added
309 (0.5 mg / l) to stain the nuclei. Afterwards the homogenate was adjusted to defined volume
310 and the mixture was kept homogenous by agitation. The total number of cells was estimated
311 by counting at least five aliquots of 10 μl using a Neubauer improved counting chamber
312 (BDH, Dagenham, Essex, UK) with an Olympus BX51 microscope equipped with
313 epifluorescence and appropriate filter settings; additional aliquots were counted if needed to
314 reach the coefficient of variation among counts ≤ 0.10 . The proportion of neurons was
315 determined by immunocytochemical detection of the neuronal nuclear marker NeuN⁶³. This
316 neuron-specific protein was detected by an anti-NeuN mouse monoclonal antibody (clone
317 A60, Sigma-Aldrich; dilution 1:800), which was characterized by Western blotting with chick
318 brain samples and shown to react with a protein of the same molecular weight as in mammals,
319 indicating that it does not cross-react with other proteins in birds⁶⁴. The binding sites of the
320 primary antibody were revealed by Alexa Fluor 546-conjugated goat anti-mouse IgG antibody
321 (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA; dilution 1:400). An electronic hematologic counter
322 (Alchem Grupa, Torun, Poland) was used to count the proportion of double-labelled nuclei in
323 the Neubauer chamber. At least 500 nuclei were examined for each sample. The final data set
324 included information on neuron numbers for 240 specimens belonging to 111 species. For
325 *Caloenas nicobarica* and *Eudromia Formosa*, information on pallial neurons was missing and
326 had to be imputed to avoid comparing results with different sample sizes. We estimated these
327 missing data by combining phylogenetic imputation with multivariate data (brain and body
328 size, and number of neurons in the entire brain, the pallium, the cerebellum and the brainstem),
329 as implemented in the R-package *phytools*⁶⁵. We note that results hold whether or not these
330 two species were included in the analyses.

331

332 **Innovation data.** Our innovation data were taken from Lefebvre⁴², compiled by
333 systematically searching for reports of new behaviours in the short notes of 204 ornithology
334 journals published between 1960 and 2020. The criterion to accept an innovation was that the
335 report described the behaviour with key words such as ‘novel’, ‘not noted before’ and/or
336 ‘unusual’. Each innovation was classified as a resource innovation —if it involved a novel
337 food item—, or a technical innovation —if the searching and handling techniques were
338 themselves novel regardless of whether the food type was novel or not⁵. Nocturnal clades
339 were excluded due to the difficulty of being observed. The frequency with which a species
340 was observed innovating in the wild was used to characterize the propensity of the species to
341 innovate. Innovation propensity depends not only on innovative ability, however, but also on
342 the probability that new behaviours are observed and reported. Thus, a species may have a
343 low number of innovations not because it cannot innovate but because it is rare or secretive,
344 and hence difficult to observe and study. We tackled this issue by considering research effort
345 in the analyses^{5,11,31}, using data on number of papers published per species⁶⁶. The probability
346 of reporting an innovation may also increase with geographic range, urbanisation and island
347 living, and it can decrease with migratory behaviour^{5,11,31}. Therefore, we also included these
348 variables as covariates in the models (see below). Data were drawn from previously
349 assembled datasets. Geographic range (number of 1 degree x 1 degree grid cells overlapping
350 breeding/resident range), mobility (resident, nomadic, migrant and altitudinal migrant) and
351 insularity (proportion of breeding/resident range intersecting with islands of landmass below
352 2,000 sq km) were extracted from⁶⁷, while the occurrence in urban environments was taken
353 from¹¹.

354

355 **Life history data.** We extracted published information on the duration of incubation
356 (embryonic stage) and fledging periods (post-natal growth) from previously compiled
357 datasets^{11,31}, updated with information from the online edition of the Handbook of birds of
358 the world (<https://birdsoftheworld.org>). Information was available for 108 species for
359 incubation duration and 102 species for fledging duration. Post-natal growth fraction was
360 estimated as $[\text{fledging}/(\text{incubation} + \text{fledging})]^{0.5}$, following⁶⁸. To assign species to different
361 developmental modes, we used the classification recently proposed by Bothelo⁶⁹, which
362 divides species in super-precocial, precocial, semi-precocial, semi-altricial, altricial and
363 super-altricial. However, for the questions addressed in the study, and because some
364 categories were insufficiently represented in our data set, we pooled together super-precocial,
365 precocial and semi-precocial species in a general precocial category and semi-altricial,
366 altricial and super-altricial species in an altricial category.

367

368 **Modelling neurons, brains and innovations.** We used Bayesian Generalised Linear Mixed
369 models (BGLMM) based on Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approximations to model
370 variation in neuron numbers, brain size and innovation propensity, as implemented in the R-
371 packages *MCMCglmm*⁴⁶ and *BRMS*⁷⁰. To ensure that neuron numbers and brain measures
372 were species characters, we first used intra-specific data to assess within-species consistency
373 by means of Gaussian BGLMM, including sex as fixed effect and species as random effect
374 (**Supplementary Table 3**). Consistency was estimated as the Intraclass Correlation
375 Coefficient (ICC), calculated by dividing the variation among species by the total variation
376 (i.e. variation among species plus variation within species, the latter including natural
377 variation and measurement error). The consistency attributed to shared ancestors was
378 estimated in a similar model, but incorporating a variance-covariance matrix of phylogenetic
379 distances as a random effect. This allowed us estimating varying intercepts among species
380 adjusted by phylogenetic dependency. Phylogenetic heritability was estimated as the fraction
381 of total variation accounted for the phylogenetic distance between species (**Supplementary**
382 **Table 3**).

383 To test whether neuron numbers affect innovation frequency, we then averaged the
384 values for each species and used phylogenetic BGLMMs with the response variable
385 (innovation frequency) fitted as Gaussian. In these models, biogeographic realm⁷¹ was
386 included as a random effect together with the phylogenetic variance-covariance matrix to
387 allow the integration of global information originating from different regions³¹. To control
388 for potential confounding effects, research effort, geographic range, tolerance to urbanisation,
389 insularity and mobility were included as fixed effects.

390 Species-level phylogenetic BGLMMs were also used to model neuron numbers as a
391 function of body mass, development duration (incubation and fledging) and incubation
392 fraction. We generally used BRMS with Gaussian responses, switching to Weibull
393 distributions when divergent transitions affected model convergence. To assess whether the
394 relationship varied between low-slope and highest-slope grades, sensu Ksepka et al.⁵², we
395 included in the models an interaction with a variable coding for these two groups. Differences
396 between precocial and altricial species was investigated in a similar way.

397 The phylogenetic hypothesis was a summary trees based on 10,000 trees from one of
398 the backbones of the complete phylogeny of birds⁷² available at www.birdtree.org. We note
399 that using the alternative phylogenetic backbone yielded similar results.

400 For all models, the number of MCMC iterations and the burn-in interval were chosen
401 so as to ensure satisfactory convergence. The priors settings are described in the
402 Supplementary R code. The parameters reported for fixed and random effects are the posterior
403 mode and the 95% lower and upper credibility intervals (CI). We considered the fixed effects

404 statistically significant when 95% CIs did not include the zero. Conditional effects plots and
405 95% credible intervals were used to visualize the relationship between predictors and response
406 variables.

407

408

409 **Describing neuron numbers as a function of relative and absolute brain size.** We used
410 regression-based Random Forests (RF), a type of machine-learning algorithm, to describe
411 neuron numbers as a function of both absolute and relative brain size⁷³. When modelling
412 quantitative response variables, RF uses linear regressions to recursively partition the data by
413 means of decision trees. Instead of selecting a best tree, however, the method does so by
414 taking a random sample of the training data and a random selection of variables at each step⁴⁵.
415 For each tree in the RF, the fitted value of each terminal node is the mean of the response
416 variable values, which is averaged over all trees to estimate the fitted values of the RF. The
417 data not used to train the model, the out-of-bag (OOB) sample, provides a way to stabilise the
418 error without having to sacrifice training data to use for validation. In this way, RF allows to
419 efficiently model non-linear relationships and deal with complex interactions between
420 predictors while avoiding over-fitting, producing stable patterns that are more difficult to
421 change with new data and that are less sensitive to outliers.

422 We modelled neuron numbers (response variable) as a function of relative and
423 absolute brain size (predictors) with the R-package *randomForest*⁷⁴. Following the protocol
424 suggested by Briec et al.⁴⁵, we ran 500 trees twice and compared the stability of the results
425 (correlation >0.97 in all cases). Deviations between the fitted and observed values were used
426 to compute a “pseudo” R². Bi-variate partial dependence (i.e., marginal effects) plots for the
427 last tree in the forest, once the model had converged, were used to visualize the co-variation
428 of neuron numbers with absolute and relative brain size while univariate plots were used to
429 visualize the influence of each predictor separately.

430 To be included together with absolute brain size in the RF, we estimated relative brain
431 size by means of the *normalized scaled brain index*⁶¹ (NSBI). This approach uses the equation
432 of allometric growth to adjust the brain size of species to that which they would have if all
433 had the same body size, making the values directly comparable:

434
$$NSBI = Y_i \left[\frac{X_0}{X_i} \right]^b$$

435 where b is the allometric exponent, Y_i and X_i are, respectively, brain size and body size for the
436 individual i and X_0 is the ancestral body size used to scale all species to the same size. We
437 estimated the allometric exponent b based on a log-log phylogenetic Gaussian BGLMMs of
438 absolute brain size against body mass. To this purpose, we used a previously assembled
439 dataset of brain mass (g) and volume (ml)⁷⁵, updated with information on brain mass from

440 the specimens used to estimate neuron numbers (see above) and with new endocast measures
441 of specimens from museums in Europe and North America ($n = 114$ specimens). Volumes
442 were obtained by means of the endocast method and converted to mass by multiplying by the
443 density of brain tissue (i.e. 1.036g ml^{-1})⁷⁵. We only used specimens of known body mass,
444 yielding information for 10,523 specimens belonging to 1,977 species. To scale all species to
445 the same size, we used the body mass of the presumed ancestor of current birds (2400 g), as
446 suggested by Torres et al.⁷⁶. In our dataset, for example, the greater adjutant (*Leptoptilos*
447 *dubius*) has the largest brain (~34g) of the 1976 species from our dataset but this mainly
448 reflects the fact that it is a large bird (~7400g). Using the above normalization technique to
449 scale the brain, the NSBI of the greater adjutant (*Leptoptilos dubius*) —estimated around
450 6.29— brings the species down to the 300th position of the ranking.

451 The NSBI is equivalent to the residual approach used in previous studies and hence
452 presumes that species share the same brain:body allometric equation. However, there is
453 evidence that the allometric exponent can exhibit some differences across lineages⁵².
454 Consequently, we used a second NSBI (NSBI_{grades}) based on an allometric exponent b
455 estimated excluding clades that have been found to exhibit substantial grade shifts in
456 brain:body allometries (i.e. *Anseriformes* and *Neoaves*)⁵². This exponent represents the
457 scaling relationship of birds before some lineages experienced grade shifts (**Fig. 1**), and it is
458 remarkably close to that estimated with the entire dataset (**Supplementary Fig. 11**). Thus, in
459 the main text we present the results based on the NSBI_{grades}, which better fit to the proposed
460 theoretical framework (**Fig. 1**).

461

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662

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665 CO collected the neuroanatomical data, LL the innovation data, and JGP and FS the
666 endocast data; DS designed and conducted the analyses, with contributions of FS, LL,
667 PN and TM; DS wrote the manuscript and all authors edited and approved it.

668

669 **Competing interests:** The authors declare no competing interests.

670 **Figures**
671

672 **Fig. 1. Framework linking cognition, neuron numbers and brain size.** **a**, Enhanced
673 cognition is assumed to require more neurons in the pallial telencephalon, and perhaps also
674 in the cerebellum. Thus, an increase in pallial neurons relative to the ancestors is expected in
675 lineages that have been selected for higher intelligence. **b**, Because pallium comprises a large
676 fraction of the mass of the brain, a disproportionate accumulation of pallial neurons should
677 enlarge the brain relative to body size. **c**, If the benefits of enhanced cognition increase with
678 body size, selection for cognition should further increase brain size in large species. As a
679 result, species that excel at cognitive performance should have brains that are large in both
680 absolute and relative terms. **d**, A mechanism that may allow accumulation of more neurons
681 in the pallium is to extend the period of development, particularly in the later stages.
682 According to some evo-devo theories, extending the later stages of development increases
683 neurogenesis in the areas of the brain where progenitor cell multiplication stops later, i.e. the
684 pallial areas of the telencephalon. Thus, if a longer development period facilitates
685 neurogenesis in pallial regions, it may be targeted by selection for increased intelligence. **e**,
686 Phylogenetic relationships among the species analysed for neuron numbers to address
687 hypotheses b-c (for an enlarged tree with species names see Supplementary Fig. 1). Silhouette
688 illustrations are from PhyloPic (<http://phylopic.org>), contributed by Anthony Caravaggi and
689 Ferran Sayol under public domain licence.

690

691 **Fig. 2. Neurons and innovation propensity.** Relationship between neuron numbers and
 692 innovation propensity for the entire brain and the pallium, cerebellum and brainstem, as
 693 predicted by models. **a**, Absolute neuron numbers. **b**, Neuron numbers adjusted by body size
 694 by including body mass (previously subtracting brain mass) as co-variate in the model. **c**,
 695 Density of neurons (cells per mg). All models account for the effect of phylogeny,
 696 biogeographic realm and confounding variables (see Supplementary Tables 1 and 2 for
 697 details). Lines and credibility intervals are derived from Bayesian phylogenetic mixed
 698 models. Sample size is 99 species, as nocturnal specialists (i.e. owls) are excluded from the
 699 innovation database.

700

701 **Fig. 3. Neuron numbers and brain mass as a function of body size.** **a-b**, Distribution of
702 neuron numbers among pallium, cerebellum and brainstem for clades belonging to low-slope
703 (a) and the highest slope (b) grades. The assignment of species to each slope grade group is
704 based on Ksepka et al.⁵². **c**, Variation in neuron numbers in the entire brain as a function of
705 body size. **d-e**, Variation in brain mass as a function of body size for the sample of species
706 used in analyses of neurons (d) and for the entire brain-body data set (e). In c-d, clades with
707 low-slope grades are shown in blue while clades with the highest slope grades are shown in
708 red. In all plots, owls have been excluded. For plots based on the entire sample of species, see
709 Supplementary Fig. 3.
710

711 **Fig. 4. Neuron numbers as a function of absolute and relative brain size.** **a**, Bivariate
712 dependence plots representing neuron numbers in the entire brain and main brain regions as
713 a function of absolute and relative brain size, based on the predictions from random forests.
714 Colours describe neuron numbers, with low numbers represented by dark-blue colours and
715 higher numbers by yellow-green colours. Relative brain size was estimated by means of the
716 *normalized scaled brain index*⁶¹, with the allometric exponent estimated excluding clades that
717 have been found to exhibit substantial grade shifts in brain:body allometries
718 (NSBI_{grades}, see Methods). **b**, Univariate representations (partial dependence plots) for
719 relative brain size to further interpret the bivariate dependence plots. The plots show the
720 dependence between neuron numbers and relative brain size, marginalizing over the values
721 of absolute brain size. **c**, Univariate representation of the bivariate dependence plot for
722 absolute brain size. In all analyses, owls have been excluded. For analyses with the entire
723 sample of species, see Supplementary Figs. 6 and 7.
724

725 **Fig. 5. Neurons and development in species belonging to low- and the highest slope**
 726 **grades.** Neuron numbers as a function of the duration of development (embryonic stage plus
 727 post-natal growth)(a) and the fraction of total development time represented by the post-natal
 728 growth (b), for low-slope grades (blue bar) and the highest slope grades (red bar). Lines and
 729 credibility intervals are derived from Bayesian phylogenetic mixed models. In all analyses,
 730 owls have been excluded (for analyses with the entire sample size, see Supplementary Fig.
 731 8).

